

Guidance on Creating Acceptable CMIP Experiment Names¹

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When MIPs define experiments, they must specify the experiment conditions, including boundary conditions and external forcings and usually a start date and duration of the experiment, along with any other imposed requirements. Once an experiment has been defined, it must be assigned a unique short name, which will be relied on by the MIP supporting software infrastructure for uniquely identifying datasets and managing the data. These short names will typically also be used by researchers in, for example, journal articles to identify the experiment when describing results and as labels in the figures they produce.

The short names obviously cannot describe in any detail what the experiment conditions are; that must be done using longer, more descriptive names and by documenting the experiment conditions.

To ensure within a given CMIP phase that all the short names are unique, participating MIPs must [submit their proposed short names](#) for review by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP). In addition to ensuring uniqueness, the WIP may suggest changes to submitted names that are inconsistent with the naming rules developed over past CMIP phases. By ensuring consistency of names across MIPs and across phases of CMIP, it will be easier for users to interpret them.

Before constructing a new short experiment name, please review the [CMIP6 names](#). These are largely consistent with CMIP5 names (see appendix 1.1 of the [CMIP5 DRS document](#)), but prior to CMIP6, hyphens were not permitted in experiment names so some names were modified for clarity.

In defining an experiment short name, the following rules are especially important:

1. **Consistency:** If the experiment is the same as in an earlier CMIP phase (but perhaps with updated boundary conditions, forcing and temporal extent), adopt the same name as before. If an experiment is similar to an earlier one but judged to be enough different to warrant assignment of a different short name, construct the name along the lines of the earlier one. In general, the descriptor vocabulary should be consistent within CMIP7 and with earlier phases. DECK experiment identifiers (amip, 1pctCO2, abrupt-4xCO2, piControl, historical, esm-piControl, esm-historical, piClim-*, etc) cannot be used, these experiment names anchor DECK continuity across phases.
2. **Structure:** Short names are usually constructed by concatenating a few short text strings describing the experiment. For example, "abrupt-4xCO2" refers to an abrupt forcing change

¹The guidance summarized here was developed and evolved over several phases of CMIP. It may be expected to continue to slowly evolve to meet unanticipated future requirements.

experiment in which the CO₂ concentration is instantaneously quadrupled relative to pre-industrial conditions. Sometimes the concatenated descriptor elements simply run together (e.g., "A4SSTice"), but usually the names are easier to decipher if the separate descriptor elements are exposed using the "camel case"² approach (e.g., "piControl") or by simply inserting a hyphen (e.g., "abrupt-4xCO₂"). Usually there would be no need for more than 3 descriptor elements and sometimes a single descriptor would be sufficient to uniquely identify an experiment. When there are 3 descriptor elements separated by hyphens, they usually distinguish between an experiment group, a member of the group, and the experiment variants. The group name appears first and the variant descriptor last. For example, the "aqua-control" and "aqua-p4K" are both aqua-planet experiments, but in the second, the prescribed SSTs are +4K warmer. Each of these experiments include "lwoff" as a third descriptor element to indicate the longwave cloud radiative effects have been turned off (e.g., "aqua-control-lwoff"), which distinguishes them from the experiments that include the cloud radiative effects.

3. **Allowed characters:** All experiment short names must be constructed using only the following characters: a-z, A-Z, 0-9, and the hyphen ("-"). Note that, in particular, underscores, periods, and spaces are prohibited. This restriction on the permitted character set is imposed because the infrastructure interprets certain characters as text string separators that are treated specially.
4. **Capitalization:** Capital letters should be used sparingly and normally only for the following purposes:
 - a. For consistency with CMIP6 usage.
 - b. To embed a very common acronym in the short name (e.g., "a4SST", "histGHG"). Less well-known acronyms, such as "PI" (pre-industrial) should be written in lower case (e.g., "piControl")
 - c. For construction of "camel case" strings that facilitate human readability (e.g., "piControl")
 - d. To name common chemical species (e.g., "1pctCO₂")

The first character of an experiment name is normally not capitalized.

5. **Length:** For CMIP7, an exceptional justification will be required for approval of an experiment name longer than 20 characters. Most names should be shorter than 14 characters because experiment names, along with 8 other descriptors of the dataset (e.g., source, variable name, frequency) will appear in every filename in the CMIP data archive. Limiting filenames to no more than, say, 80 characters (in order to fit the names on a typical page width), means the average length of a descriptor should be about 9 characters. In CMIP6 the median length of an experiment short name was 13; the shortest name was 2 characters, but this was an exception. Only 4 of 322 CMIP6 experiment names were longer than 24 characters. Short names will likely be more readily adopted by users in referring to an experiment in a journal article or in labeling curves in a graph.

² "Camel case" is used to concatenate several words or acronyms or abbreviations into a string without separating them by spaces but rather by indicating the start of each element by capitalizing its first letter. The first word of the string is usually not capitalized. For example, "piControl" is in "camel case", and the abbreviation "pi" stands for pre-industrial, and it is followed by the word "Control", which is begun with an upper case "C".